

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Women are more susceptible than men to micronutrient depletion during petrol exposure

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ABSTRACT

The influence of gender on the modulating effects of many xenobiotics has been suggested. The aim of the study is to determine which of the genders, is more at risk of altered micronutrient status subsequent to petroleum-product exposure. 60 petrol-station attendants (PSA) as well as 60 control participants were recruited for the study. The test or control group for each gender consisted of 30 participants. Serum obtained from five millimeters of blood was used to determine the levels of micronutrients. Vitamins and trace elements were determined using High Performance Liquid Chromatography and Atomic Absorption Spectrometry respectively. Significant differences between groups were ascertained using Student's t test. Correlation study between length of service (at petrol station) and micronutrient levels was determined using Pearson's correlation co-efficient. $P < 0.05$ was considered significant. Although correlation was observed between length of service and several micronutrients for both male and female PSA and petrol caused significant reduction in micronutrient levels in both groups of PSA; Mo, Fe and Se, pyridoxine, niacin, vitamins E and vitamin C were more significantly lower in female PSA than male ones. These results suggest that women are more susceptible than men to micronutrient depletion during petrol exposure.

Keywords: Male; Female; Vitamins; Minerals; Petrol station attendants.

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INTRODUCTION

A number of chemicals have been identified that alter levels of essential vitamins and minerals in the human body [1]. While some of them are household products that are required for every day existence; some others are of therapeutic importance [2, 3]. Gasoline is a modern day necessity. Petroleum products are employed as fuel for industrial use as well as to power automobiles or other machines [4]. Several millions of litres of gasoline are sold every day in Nigeria. The properties of its components make contact with humans unavoidable.

Gasoline is a refined product of crude oil that contains more than 150 hydrocarbons with a range of boiling point from 40°C to 180°C [5]. Hydrocarbon content of gasoline include alkanes (paraffins), isoparaffins, alkenes (olefins) and naphthenics, its aromatic compounds are benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene and xylene [5]. Many of these components are known to be volatile [6].

Slight differences in physiology have been ascribed to be the basis of great variations in response to xenobiotic exposure even within the same species. The male hormone testosterone has been identified to enhance the toxicity of high doses of acetaminophen [7]. In

addition, a more pronounced hepatotoxic and carcinogenic effect of aflatoxin B1 in males than females is well documented. Such that in parts of the world where aflatoxin B1 contamination of crops is common and it has been identified as a casual agent that synergistically interacts with hepatitis B virus infection in the pathogenesis (etiologic factor) of hepatocellular carcinoma, the incidence of hepatocellular carcinoma is in the ratio of 4: 1 in favor of women [8]. A higher level of oxidative stress has also been recognized in female subjects exposed to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons when compared with males [9].

Many of the components of antioxidant defense system (including antioxidant micronutrients) are sometimes altered in human subjects as a result of oxidative-stress induced xenobiotic administration. The objective of this study is to determine the deleterious effect of petroleum product exposure on serum micronutrient levels of male and female PSA as well as investigate which of the two groups is more susceptible to such exposure.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Subjects

Being a pilot study, the sample size of the studied population was 60 persons (30 participants for each gender). Adults above the age of 19 years, who have worked consistently in petrol station for at least 5 years, with between 8-10 hours of daily work shift were recruited for the study. Not more than 2 petrol station attendants (PSA) were recruited from any petrol station; none of the stations captured in the study had less than 10 attendants on their payroll. Random sampling technique was employed not only to recruit petrol station attendants that met the inclusion criteria, but also used in selection of the petrol stations captured in the study.

Individuals were assisted in filling questionnaire and the information provided was used in selecting suitable participants that met the inclusion criteria. The questionnaire was constructed to obtain information on their socio-economic/demographic status (age, gender, income, educational level); medical state (disease, medication) lifestyle (smoking pattern, alcohol consumption, etc); as well as occupational information (duration of exposure to petroleum products/length of service at petrol station, number of shift per week, number of hours per shift). Equally information was obtained about use of protective gears (face mask, gloves, overall). Confidentiality was maintained with regard to the information provided by the respondents.

A total of 60 participants (30 for each gender) above the age of 19 years were also selected from the

general population. They had not been involved in any occupations associated with exposure to gasoline/diesel (e.g. automobile mechanic workshops or automobile fuelling stations). Because of the volatile nature of gasoline and since many of the filling stations are located in residential quarters, during subject recruitment process; every effort was made to ensure that control subjects were not living in very close proximity to petrol/filling stations. In Nigeria, it is a common knowledge that during petroleum product scarcity, these products are bought into containers to be emptied into fuel tanks of automobiles/motorcycles, therefore commercial car drivers and motorcycle riders were also excluded as control subjects. Other exclusion criteria for test and control groups include micronutrient supplementation as well as any disease capable of altering serum micronutrient levels. Moreover, lifestyle was also considered as exclusion criterion; all participants with lifestyles capable of altering micronutrient levels were not recruited for the study. Since socio-economic markers have been identified to have impact on levels of micronutrients, all participants recruited for the study were of the same socio-economic status; income, education and occupation were markers adopted for this purpose.

Informed consent was obtained from each subject prior to the commencement of the study. Five millimeters of venous blood was taken from antecubital vein of each participant and dispensed into anti-coagulant and micronutrient free bottles. They were delivered to the laboratory not more than 2 hours after collection. The samples were then centrifuged and sera stored at -20°C until the period of analysis. All samples were obtained during work shift before noon (12:00). All procedures were carried out in accordance with revised Helsinki Declaration (1983).

Micronutrient analysis

Serum levels of vitamins A, B₆, C, D and E, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, and folic acid were determined by employing High Performance Liquid Chromatographic technique (HPLC). Quantification of serum concentrations of Zn, Cu, Se, Mn, Co, Fe, Mo, and Cr took place using the Atomic Absorption Spectrometric method. Waters® Corporation Milford, Massachusetts USA supplied HPLC equipment whereas Buck Scientific 205 Atomic Absorption spectrometry was supplied by Buck Scientific in East Norwalk, Connecticut (USA). Each of the reagents utilized in the estimation of the micronutrients was of high-purity analytical grade (Merck, Darmstadt; BDH Chemicals Ltd). The water employed for the preparation of reagents and working standard was deionized, doubly distilled and re-

deionized prior to the commencement of the experiment (Millipore Co., Bedford, MA), and had specific resistance of $>3 \text{ M}\Omega$. Working standard was made from spectroscopic stock standard (1g/l) that was supplied by Buck Scientific. In addition all disposable apparatus was vigorously washed before use by immersing in concentrated nitric acid and thoroughly rinsed with the same deionized, doubly distilled and redeionized water.

Statistical analysis

All analyses were done using SPSS version 15. Significant differences between male and female PSA as well as between PSA of each gender and their respective control were determined using Student's t test. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used for correlation analysis. A p value of ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

Results of the study are presented in Tables 1-4. Shown in Table 1 are the serum levels of vitamins and minerals of male petrol station attendants (PSA) and male control subjects. Of all the micronutrients estimated only riboflavin, pyridoxine, niacin, vitamin D, Se, Cr, and Mo were not significantly different ($p>0.05$) in male PSA

compared with control, all others (vitamins A, C, E, thiamine, folic, Zn, Cu, Mn, Co, Fe) were significantly lower ($p<0.05$). The results of serum micronutrients of female PSA and female control group are presented in Table 2, vitamins A, C, E, thiamine, niacin, folic, Zn, Cu, Mn, Cr, Co, and Fe were significantly lower ($p<0.05$) in female PSA compared with female control whereas riboflavin, pyridoxine, vitamin D, Se, and Mo were not significantly different ($p>0.05$). When the results of serum micronutrients of both female and male PSA were compared in Table 3; riboflavin, thiamine, vitamins A and D, as well as Zn, Mn, and Cr were not significantly different ($p>0.05$) in both groups whereas folic acid, niacin, vitamin C and E, Se, Fe, Mo and Co were significantly lower ($p<0.05$) in female PSA compared with male while pyridoxine and Cu were significantly higher ($p<0.05$).

The results of the personal/basic characteristics of both males and females PSA are presented in Table 4. Age, duration of employment time/length of service at petrol station(s), number of shift per week, and number of hours per shift were not significantly different for both groups. None of the PSA had used facemasks in the preceding 24 months; none of the male PSA but 3 of female PSA had utilized the protective gear- hand gloves in the past 12 months.

Table 1. Serum levels of micronutrients of male petrol station attendants and control subjects.

Micronutrients	Male Control (n =30)	Male PSA (n =30)	p-value
Riboflavin (nmol/l)	614.67±31.72	620.11± 20.83	0.702
Folic (nmol/l)	18.43±3.87	15.04±6.60	0.026 ^a
Pyridoxine (nmol/l)	72.45±7.71	70.68±4.95	0.401
Niacin (nmol/l)	19.31±17.29	18.63±15.38	0.640
Thiamine (nmol/l)	144.70±22.59	130.90±30.22	0.018 ^a
Vitamin D (nmol/l)	98.21±5.48	97.52±11.70	0.092
Vitamin E (µmol/l)	25.21±7.00	20.27±6.64	0.014 ^a
Vitamin C (mmol/l)	59.09±6.26	51.62±9.04	0.022 ^a
Vitamin A (µmol/l)	2.01±0.16	1.70±0.10	0.009 ^a
Se (µmol/l)	1.28±0.23	1.16±0.24	0.078
Cu (µmol/l)	17.06±4.37	14.55±3.85	0.019 ^a
Fe (µg/dl)	144.89±16.31	131.30±31.07	0.032 ^a
Mo (nmol/l)	21.00±1.87	22.26±4.48	0.384
Zn (µmol/l)	16.12±4.03	13.33±3.69	0.041 ^a
Mn (nmol/l)	14.50±3.13	11.64±2.06	0.017 ^a
Cr (nmol/l)	1.92±0.03	1.99±0.14	0.059
Co (nmol/l)	4.94±0.79	3.14±0.92	0.025 ^a

Results are expressed as mean±standard deviation. ^a Significant difference when male petrol station attendants and control were compared. p value ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

Table 2. Serum levels of micronutrients of female petrol station attendants and control subjects.

Micronutrients	Female Control (n =30)	Female PSA (n =30)	p-value
Riboflavin (nmol/l)	639.06±40.91	633.27±26.70	0.912
Folic (nmol/l)	17.75±3.33	12.33±3.90	0.019 ^b
Pyridoxine (nmol/l)	83.30±7.98	80.39±5.43	0.162
Niacin (nmol/l)	18.74±22.82	15.85±8.17	0.038 ^b
Thiamine (nmol/l)	132.99±28.07	122.41±15.40	0.040 ^b
Vitamin D (nmol/l)	92.17±9.04	94.08±5.05	0.066
Vitamin E (µmol/l)	26.74±5.40	16.30±3.92	0.024 ^b
Vitamin C (mmol/l)	63.67±9.39	44.01±4.48	0.011 ^b
Vitamin A (µmol/l)	1.96.08±0.12	1.62±0.22	0.119 ^b
Se (µmol/l)	1.30±0.45	1.00±0.09	0.051
Cu (µmol/l)	22.97±8.03	18.36±5.45	0.037 ^b
Fe (µg/dl)	122.58±20.22	109.80±27.74	0.029 ^b
Mo (nmol/l)	19.93±3.39	18.32±5.00	0.553
Zn (µmol/l)	15.29±6.61	12.29±4.43	0.014 ^b
Mn (nmol/l)	15.91±4.06	12.77±2.93	0.013 ^b
Cr (nmol/l)	1.98±0.08	1.84±0.11	0.020 ^b
Co (nmol/l)	5.57±0.52	4.41±0.50	0.012 ^b

Results are expressed as mean±standard deviation. ^b Significant difference when female petrol station attendants and control were compared. p value ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

Table 3. Serum levels of micronutrients of male and female petrol station attendants.

Micronutrients	Male PSA (n =30)	Female PSA (n =30)	p-value
Riboflavin (nmol/l)	620.11± 20.83	633.27±26.70	0.406
Folic (nmol/l)	15.04±6.60	12.33±3.90	0.049 ^c
Pyridoxine (nmol/l)	70.68±4.95	80.39±5.43	0.037 ^c
Niacin (nmol/l)	18.63±15.38	15.85±8.17	0.042 ^c
Thiamine (nmol/l)	130.90±30.22	122.41±15.40	0.311
Vitamin D (nmol/l)	97.52±11.70	94.08±5.05	0.172
Vitamin E (µmol/l)	20.27±6.64	16.30±3.92	0.040 ^c
Vitamin C (mmol/l)	51.62±9.04	44.01±4.48	0.024 ^c
Vitamin A (µmol/l)	1.70±0.10	1.62±0.22	0.533
Se (µmol/l)	1.16±0.24	1.00±0.09	0.037 ^c
Cu (µmol/l)	14.55±3.85	18.36±5.45	0.042 ^c
Fe (µg/dl)	131.30±31.07	109.80±27.74	0.033 ^c
Mo (nmol/l)	22.26±4.48	18.32±5.00	0.014 ^c
Zn (µmol/l)	13.33±3.69	12.29±4.43	0.310
Mn (nmol/l)	11.64±2.06	12.77±2.93	0.199
Cr (nmol/l)	1.99±0.14	1.84±0.11	0.701
Co (nmol/l)	3.14±0.92	4.41±0.50	0.113 ^c

Results are expressed as mean±standard deviation. ^c Significant difference when male and female petrol station attendants were compared. p value ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

Table 4. Personal/basic characteristics of petrol station attendants (female and male) and control.

	Male PSA (n =30)	Female PSA (n =30)	P value
Age (years)	26.90±4.2	28.20±5.3	0.471
Duration of employment at petrol station (years)	5.75±1.0	6.25±2.2	0.339
Number of shifts per week	6.50±0.9	6.10±1.2	0.720
Number of hours per shift	9.50±2.1	8.60±3.8	0.096

Results are expressed as mean±standard deviation. p value ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

These 3 female did so because of dermal sensitivity to petrol; they revealed that contact with petrol resulted in skin irritation, even then hand glove was infrequently employed. All PSA reported infrequent use of overall although its frequency of use was higher in female than male PSA. In addition, in stations where overall were not provided but petrol station uniform made available, more females employed the use of work uniform than males. This was not considered as overall. In female PSA correlation was noted between length of service at petrol station and zinc ($r = -0.419$, $p = 0.024$), Cr ($r = 0.382$, $p = 0.045$), Co ($r = -0.477$, $p = 0.010$), and folic acid ($r = -0.581$, $p = 0.038$) but only zinc ($r = -0.371$, $p = 0.049$), Cu ($r = 0.609$, $p = 0.006$), and folic acid ($r = -0.369$, $p = 0.045$) were correlated with length of service at petrol station in male PSA.

DISCUSSION

Self-servicing at fuel filling station is common in industrialized parts of the world, but this is not so for many developing nations where the pumps are manned by attendants. Because of the nature of petroleum products, especially its volatile property, exposure of their toxic constituents to people within petrol station vicinity cannot be ruled out. Some job types, and life-style as well as exposure to toxic and therapeutic agents are known to present with gender biased toxic response. The study of Hu et al. [10] gives an insight into a case of sex/gender bias in the disposition of an experimental animal to toxic agent exposure. Male mice were found to be more susceptible to paracetamol toxicity than female ones. Hu et al. [10] hypothesized that that was possible because of the modulating role of testosterone in paracetamol-induced toxicity. A hypothesis that was confirmed when testosterone pretreated paracetamol dosed female rats exhibited the same degree of toxicity as male rats given the same dose of paracetamol. Yet it is not only sex hormones that have been linked with differences in gender response to a toxic agent, the cytochrome P450 enzymes also have been implicated in such result outcomes. The kind of data obtained from this study; in which female petrol station attendants featured a more significant decrease in the serum levels of many of

the micronutrients than their male counterparts, is an indication that females may be more susceptible to toxic effects of gasoline exposure than males.

The constituents of crude oil and ultimately its products that the attendants are exposed to are benzene, toluene, etc. [5]. Benzene especially has been identified to be metabolized through the cytochrome P450 pathways to yield highly toxic and reactive metabolites such as benzene oxide and phenol. This may be a cause of the low levels of many of these micronutrients observed in the two categories of PSA. Many of the micronutrients possess antioxidant properties; ascorbic acid has been recognized for its notable function in regeneration of glutathione i.e. the conversion of oxidized glutathione (GSSG) to its reduced form (GSH). There is every possibility that decreased ascorbic acid level observed in PSA occurred from increased demand of the antioxidant property of GSH. Vitamin E on the other hand plays an important role in preventing lipid peroxidation. A number of essential elements (especially Zn, Cu, Mn) estimated in serum of PSA that were found to be significantly decreased have been linked with the antioxidant enzyme superoxide dismutase. An enzyme that plays vital roles in conditions of increased oxidative stress.

Occupation as a cause of infertility or sub-fertility has been observed in many different classes of artisans but Bull et al. [11] reported that paternal exposure to hydrocarbons in the occupations studied did not seem to have had a major influence on time to conception or the incidence of spontaneous abortion among the wives of the men exposed to oil products. While zinc is essential in the process of spermatogenesis, low levels of maternal folic acid which to a great extent has been linked with neural tube defects in neonates was significantly lower in female petrol station attendants compared with their male counterparts. A good percentage of female PSA are known to be within reproductive stage. The fact that serum levels of antioxidant micronutrients (Cu, Zn, vitamins C, E) of male PSA were also significantly decreased, means that male PSA may also have increased risk to several oxidative stress related diseases but the since depletion was intensified in female PSA than their male counterparts, females therefore may have elevated

risk compared with males. Supporting the possibility that petrol exposure may adversely affect the health of individuals is that not only were zinc and folic acid (essential micronutrients at all stages of human development) significantly lower in both groups of PSA when compared to their respective controls, both were also negatively correlated with length of service in PSA.

While this study has provided biochemical evidence which indicates that the consequences of petrol exposure is more grave in females than males; the cause of the significant differences in micronutrient levels of both male and female PSA may not be unassociated with dissimilarity in the physiologic make-up of both sexes, examples being sex hormone levels or differences in expression of cytochrome 450 isozymes. A wide range of microsomal enzymes (CYP2E1, CYP2F2, CYP2A6, etc) have been recognized to play a role in metabolism of constituents of petroleum products [12, 13] yielding highly reactive species capable of modulating levels of biomolecules with antioxidant potential. Moreover, it should not be surprising that the levels of Cu, vitamins C and E were lower in female PSA compared with male ones, since the expression levels of some cytochrome 450 isozymes are generally higher in females than male [14].

Even though it is speculative to suggest that either sex hormone or differences in cytochrome 450 may be responsible for differences in micronutrient presentations of both male and female PSA (as neither was included in the study), it should be worthwhile to investigate what inherent difference in male and female PSA is responsible for variations in serum micronutrient levels observed when both groups were compared. Street trading and hawking is very common in Nigeria, the use of pre-pubertal male and female hawkers who are constantly found in the filling station may help to achieve this aim. In addition such subjects can serve for longitudinal study to assess long time effect of early exposure to petroleum products.

While this study was carried out on those with closest proximity to petroleum products, filling stations are indiscriminately sited in many of the major cities in Nigeria, it can be deduced from the data obtained from the study, that female subjects who live for extended period of time in the same neighborhood as these stations may present with depletion in serum micronutrient levels. Various past studies suggest this possibility; contact with benzene (a significant component of petrol) has been reported to cause damage to DNA in traffic policemen [15], petrochemical workers [16], shoe makers [17], and printing company workers [18]. The use of protective gears has been advocated in various occupations to diminish hazard that may result in injury or illness and there is evidence to prove that if strictly adhered to, it may result in considerable protection. Since there was

general non-compliance with regard to use of protective gears by both male and female PSA, it may be postulated that such attitude contributed to the gravity of micronutrient depletion observed in both groups.

The implication of results of this kind is diverse. Essential trace elements are known for their roles as co-factors of enzymatic reactions in hundreds of chemical processes. One of the notable roles of zinc (observed to be significantly decreased in both male and female PSA) is its function in DNA repair system; the fact that this important function may be compromised by exposure to petroleum product may be postulated from results obtained through various past studies. Different markers of DNA damage have been shown to be gravely affected by petrol exposure. Using different biomarkers, such as sister chromatid exchange (SCE) or DNA strand break, Kanupriya et al. [19] demonstrated an elevation in degree of cytogenetic damage in peripheral blood lymphocytes of workers exposed to gasoline. There was also significant difference in chromosomal abnormalities between petrol-exposed workers and control especially with respect to mitotic index [20]. In addition, buccal smears collected from Nigerian petrol station pump attendants chronically exposed to petrol fumes and control, subjected to micronucleus assay showed a significant difference in micronuclei detection between the exposed and control groups, suggestive of DNA damage in petrol station pump attendants [21]. Summing up the results of many studies, Mutgud et al. [22] noted that there were increase frequency of DNA and chromosomal damage in human population exposed to petroleum products. Also according to them, mutagenic and carcinogenic effects of diesel and petroleum vapors have been reported in not only human subjects but also different biological models.

CONCLUSION

Results of this study suggest that PSA are at risk of micronutrient alteration. In addition, it seems evident that females are more at risk than males. If left unattended, exposure to petrol may increase an individual's risk to micronutrient-related diseases.

AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION

Authors contributed equally with respect to experimentation, data analysis and interpretation, and preparation of manuscript. The final manuscript has been read and approved by both authors.

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